

Soil and Crop Management

Nitrogen sources for lowland rice

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We evaluated different fertilizer N sources for efficiency in a flooded lowland soil in a farmer's field in Mahendrapalli, Kullankar, India, in 1981-82. IR20 was planted and 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha was applied. Soil was a silty clay with pH 7.2, EC 0.8 mmho/cm, 1.9% organic matter, and 329, 21.3, and 159 kg available NPK/ha.

Rice yield and available soil N at different crop stages as influenced by the different N fertilizers are in the table. Urea supergranule (USG) gave better yield than farmyard manure (FYM) and the no-N control, but was on par with

Effect of different N sources on rice yield and available soil N.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Soil available N (kg/ha)			
		Tillering	Panicle initiation	Post-harvest	Mean
Control (0, 30, 30 kg NPK/ha)	5.0	319	313	312	314
Urea best split (50% basal + 25% at tillering + 25% at panicle initiation)	6.3	353	336	321	337
50% N as FYM at puddling + 50% N as basal urea	5.8	355	350	345	350
USG	6.5	421	364	342	376
Neem cake-coated urea at planting	6.1	366	347	323	345
Lac-coated urea at planting	6.3	396	342	323	357
Urea N at planting	5.9	382	333	328	348
		Stages	Treatments	<i>S</i> × <i>T</i>	
	CD 0.6	13	23	39	
	CV% 6.0	—	7.0	—	

lac-coated urea, urea best split, neem cake-coated urea, and basal urea. Thorough incorporation of basal urea may have reduced N losses and made it perform better than was expected. We

concluded that applying N as any of these sources could increase rice yields.

In terms of maintaining soil fertility, USG was superior to other treatments. It was on par only with lac-coated urea. □

An integrated nutrient supply system for higher rice production

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Eupatorium odoratum is a noxious, fast growing weed in the humid tropics. We studied the value of *E. odoratum* compost for improving rice production.

Eupatorium and/or gliricidia compost was prepared with cow, goat, pig, or poultry manure (see table). The NPK contents of the composts, determined by chemical analysis, were almost identical.

A field experiment to determine their effect on rice growth was conducted in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Jyothi, a 110-d rice, was transplanted in Sep 1983. Different composts were applied basally at 6 t/ha and 70-35-35 kg NPK/ha was applied to provide adequate fertilization. Control plots received only NPK.

Average grain yield of rice as influenced by various composts, Kerala, India.

Treatment	NPK (%) in the composts			Yield (t/ha)
	N	P	K	
Eupatorium + cow manure	0.8	0.29	0.42	5.5
Gliricidia + cow manure	0.78	0.26	0.43	5.1
Eupatorium 50% + gliricidia 50% + cow manure	0.66	0.25	0.39	5.3
Eupatorium + goat manure	0.58	0.26	0.46	5.1
Gliricidia + goat manure	0.70	0.29	0.50	5.4
Eupatorium 50% + gliricidia 50% + goat manure	0.8	0.23	0.37	5.6
Eupatorium + poultry manure	0.65	0.33	0.40	5.2
Gliricidia + poultry manure	0.6	0.22	0.60	5.1
Eupatorium 50% + gliricidia 50% + poultry manure	0.58	0.26	0.46	5.1
Eupatorium + pig manure	0.72	0.20	0.56	5.5
Gliricidia + pig manure	0.8	0.32	0.66	5.7
Eupatorium 50% + gliricidia 50% + pig manure	0.65	0.21	0.56	5.4
Ordinary farm compost	0.8	0.33	0.95	6.2
70 - 35 - 35 kg NPK/ha	—	—	—	3.7
CD (0.05)				0.7

All composts in combination with NPK increased grain yield compared with NPK application alone (see table). Ordinary farm compost made from farm waste and cow manure performed best,

but was on par with eupatorium or gliricidia with pig manure and 50% eupatorium + 50% gliricidia with goat manure. □